

D8: Capacity and rapidity of bridge strengthening measures towards resilience quantification.

BriFace

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Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

(H2020-MSCA-IF-2018 Marie Skłodowska-Curie)

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1. Resilience components.

Resilience is a prized quality, both in organisations and individuals. It was originally a scientific term, taken from the Latin verb *salire*, to jump, and first used in English by the Jacobean experimenter Francis Bacon. The 'resilience' of a material is its ability to return to its original shape after being compressed or stretched.

Modern resilience studies originated among psychologists and psychiatrists. Researchers interested in psychological and social determinants of health picked up the concept and have gradually extended its use from the domain of mental health to health in general. Early work on resilience was concerned with the individual, but more recently researchers have become interested in resilience as a feature of whole communities. In the 20th century, developmental psychologists began applying it to children's ability to deal with trauma. Now it is a useful management concept, describing an organisation's ability to deal with change without getting bent out of shape - and staying that way.

Lately, the United Nations has announced 17 Sustainable Development Goals (Figure 1) for 2030, among which are infrastructure and sustainable cities. The concept of resilience has also passed in engineering and especially within the priorities set by the UN, there is an urgent need to come up with solutions in a resilient basis. Especially in asset management, nowadays that undoubtedly there is an everchanging environment, this approach is becoming more and more popular. The assets exhibit normal function, they are vulnerable to multiple hazards and as such the restoration of assets & networks is crucial. The main components of resilience are four (Figure 1a): i) plan, ii) absorb, iii) recover and iv) adapt. The most challenging is the quantification of resilience in order to define and draw the resilience curve (Figure 1b) throughout the lifetime of an asset. Performance indicators and assessment methods are proven to be tools that help quantify and further approach the resilience curve.

With the beginning of the 21st century, the digital revolution has underpinned most of the human activities [46]. It has the potential to deliver not only advanced communications but also groundbreaking digital solutions in critical infrastructure to ensure safety and resilience [47]. The latter means enhancing the ability to anticipate, prepare for, and adapt to changing conditions and withstand, respond to, and recover rapidly from disruptions [48]. The international literature has not exploited yet digital technologies for quantifying resilience to multiple hazards. The objective of this report is to deliver a roadmap toward resilience for transport infrastructure exposed to multiple hazards throughout their life-cycle[49], including the: (i) accumulation of damage due to human-induced stressors and/or sequences of events, which can be independent or cascading in nature, and potential exacerbation due to environmental and climate deviations [50], and (ii) abrupt disruptions after extreme hazards, not precluding that (i) might precede (ii). In this respect, the resilience of transport infrastructure is of paramount importance to world economies and societies [51] and serves the UNs Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) heavily relying upon the engineering integrity of the assets and the functionality of the networks [52]. Hence, transport infrastructure urgently needs adaptation for delivering climate resilience that is the versatility to increasing impacts and demands [104], whilst emerging technologies and digital innovation can significantly facilitate this goal.

The investment requirements toward this resilience transformation are very high. It reaches on average €688 billion per year for maintenance (EIB) of the existing economic infrastructure that is the energy, transport, water and sanitation, and telecoms [53] and €20 billion for transport infrastructure and their losses due to natural hazards [54], [55]. The expected expenditure is similar in the USA and Asia. The Transportation Research Board's (TRB) recent meetings have emphasised the significance of transport infrastructure resilience to natural hazards and climate change effects [56], [57], [58]. The American Society of Civil Engineers estimates that neglecting to act toward preserving a healthy transportation system, will have a tremendous impact on business productivity, gross domestic product (GDP), employment, personal impact and competitiveness [59]. In monetary terms, approximately \$3.9 trillion in losses, \$7 trillion in lost business sales and 2.5 million loss of jobs are expected by 2025 [60]. The

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Asian Development Bank forecasts that Asia needs to invest \$1.5 trillion a year in infrastructure from 2016 until 2030 to keep pace with economic growth. This is expected to be increased by 16% due to climate change, excluding mitigation and adaptation measures [61]. The continuous need to extend the life of transport assets [62] and to upgrade their capacity is associated with the increasing traffic loads [63], [64], as well as the environmental and human-induced hazards [65], [66], [67]. Natural hazards were proved to be exacerbated due to climate change in an ever-changing environment [68], [69], [70] imposing adaptation measures to build resilience [71], [72].

Especially in cases that strengthening measures are taken in order to make the asset recover from an incident, the rapidity is very important (Figure 3). Towards this direction, advanced strengthening systems, monitoring strategies and further indices, such as interface capacity indices, give indications of the performance and recovery of the asset, but also the ability to further withstand and adapt to a new environment and conditions.

Figure 1. United Nation's priorities.

Figure 2. The concept of resilience: a) components and b) schematic resilience curve with distinct periods of the basic components.

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Figure 3. Theoretical resilience curve.

2. Description of the strengthening techniques and their contribution to resilience.

Lately, especially with the introduction of the new components of resilience in the modern mindset of asset and network management (response, absorb, recover, adaptation) [44] the proposed scheme should be advanced in technology and simple in application, permitting at the same time fast recover and ideally undisrupted traffic/use during the intervention works (Table 1(8)). **The allocated resources and economic rationality of the bridge strengthening scheme also contributes to resilience.** The cost and duration of the structural strengthening scheme should be kept optimal and should also take into consideration the maintenance costs/resources for future response.

The efficiency of the strengthening measure is a matter of question. Each strengthening system exhibits different kind of premature/ dominant failure (Table 1(9)). Also, the same table resumes the contribution of each strengthening system to the resilience quantification (Table 1(8)). It is noted that the strengthening measures described in the table refer to composite measures, that is Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP), which is the focus of the BriFace project.

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Table 1- Summary of Bridge Strengthening Techniques

A/A	Strengthening Scheme (1)	Type (2)	Advantages (3)	Disadvantages (4)	Strengthening/control (5)	Retrofitted member (6)	Retrofitting materials (7)	Recovery contribution (8)	Dominant failure (9)
1.	Externally Bonded FRP (EB FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> plates sheets strips wraps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high strength to weight ratio⁴ ease and speed of application⁴ high corrosion resistance⁵ good bonding with epoxy-based adhesives³ undisrupted asset's operation⁴ enhancement of ductility in confinement solutions²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low temperature resistance² high cost of epoxy resins² impractical wet application² impractical application during low temperatures² poor vapor permeability² incompatibility of epoxy resin and concrete² difficult damage detection and assessment on concrete substrate² premature peeling / delamination⁵ requires surface preparation²⁰ unprotected FRP Material against wear, fire and impact loads²⁰ bond affected by aggressive environmental conditions²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural⁵ shear²⁰ compression-confinement⁵ torsional⁵ crack⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP) carbon (CFRP) aramid (AFRP) basalt (BFRP) steel (SRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> upon adhesive application, it is recommended the strip be left undisturbed for 24 hours and the structure not used for a week²⁸ application can be done without disruption of traffic⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> concrete cover separation/peeling interfacial debonding
2.	Mechanically Fastened FRP (MF FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bars strips rods fasteners threaded bolts expansion anchor bolts power-actuated fasteners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high strength to weight ratio⁴ prevents from premature peeling/delamination⁵ allows easier FRP post-tensioning⁵ surface preparation not required²⁸ ease and speed of application²⁸ good temporary measure due to reversibility²⁹ installation requires common hand tools³⁰ can be performed by unskilled labour³⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> anchors susceptible to corrosion¹⁸ less economical vs steel PT anchors¹⁸ complicated installation¹⁸ fastened joints exhibit stress concentrations¹⁹ significant slip at concrete-FRP interface²⁹ fasteners may damage concrete substrate³⁰ requires significant drilling³⁷ danger of galvanic corrosion of internal reinforcement if fasteners are in contact with steel³⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural³⁷ shear torsional crack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP) carbon (CFRP) aramid (AFRP) basalt (BFRP) steel (SRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> immediate use of the retrofitted structure²⁸ minimizing traffic delays, safety hazards, and financial losses³⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> tensile yielding & concrete crushing³⁷ concrete cover separation/peeling³⁷ bearing failure of the FRP around the interior fasteners and end anchors³⁷

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3.	Near Surface Mounted FRP (NSM FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • bars • strips • rods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high strength to weight ratio⁴ • little repair material required¹⁹ • cost effective¹⁹ • less prone to premature failure¹⁹ • better protection of FRP material against wear, fire and impact loads¹⁹ • good durability¹⁹ • good fatigue performance¹⁹ • high bond efficiency vs EB FRP⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • decreases ductility¹⁹ • debonding failure¹⁹ • requires groove preparation¹⁹ • decreases moment redistribution behaviour¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural⁶ • shear • compression²⁰ • crack¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams²⁰ • decks²⁰ • piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • glass (GFRP)⁶ • carbon (CFRP)⁶ • aramid (AFRP) • basalt (BFRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • debonding/pull-out of rods³⁸ • concrete cover separation/peeling³⁸
4.	Fibre Reinforced Cementitious Matrix (FRCM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • various configurations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high temperature resistance¹ • possible applications on wet surfaces¹ • possible applications during low temperatures¹ • compatible with concrete substrate¹ • good vapor permeability¹ • easy substrate (concrete) damage assesment²⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low bond efficiency due to mortar-based adhesive which are less effective vs epoxy resins³ • poor impregnation of fibre sheets² • premature debonding³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural¹ • shear¹ • compression/Confinement¹ • torsional¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams²⁰ • decks²⁰ • piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • glass (GFRP)¹ • carbon (CFRP)¹ • aramid (AFRP)³ • steel (SRP)¹ • Phenylene Benzobis Oxazole (PBO)¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • debonding of the internal matrix layer³⁹
5.	Sprayed FRP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • short randomly oriented chopped fibres • polymer matrix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • avoids unidirectional composite material¹⁷ • suitable for complex surfaces, geometries & joints¹⁷ • forms a continuous strengthening layer¹⁷ • enhanced bonding vs EBFPR¹⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • quality control issues of mixing the fibres and resins⁴⁰ • requires surface preparation¹⁷ • practical limitations in fibre placement around sharp corners²¹ • premature debonding²¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural⁵ • shear²¹ • compression/confinement⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams²⁰ • decks²⁰ • piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • glass (GFRP)²⁰ • carbon (CFRP)²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fracturing and debonding of FRP⁴⁰ • concrete crushing and yielding of steel⁴⁰
6.	Steel Plate Brackets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • steel Plate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • potential enhancement of beam ductility²³ • ease of application²³ • increase member stiffness⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase in selfweight²⁵ • undesirable change in stiffness²⁵ • higher weight to strength ratio²⁵ • debonding⁸ • required handling heavy parts²⁵ • corrosion of plates²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural⁸ • shear⁸ • compression/confinement²⁰ • torsional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams²⁰ • decks²⁰ • piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • steel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no traffic disruption²⁷ • short construction period²³ • possible application under traffic loads²³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • debonding of steel plate⁸ • diagonal tension failure beams suffering from corrosion⁸
7.	External Post Tensioning (Steel strands)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ease of inspection⁹ • speed of installation⁹ • cost effective⁹ • low increase in deadload¹¹ • tendons can be replaced / restressed¹⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tendons susceptible to corrosion¹⁰ • prestress force decreases over time¹² • requires concrete in good condition¹¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • deflection²⁰ • crack control¹¹ • flexural¹¹ • shear¹¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams²⁰ • decks²⁰ • piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • steel strands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low disturbance to traffic flow⁹ • minimum disruption to existing structure⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • crushing of concrete^{9,11}

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • difficult Anchorage installation¹¹ • shear capacity difficult to determine¹¹ • potential ductility reduction¹¹ • aesthetics¹¹ 						
8.	Concrete Section Enlargement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • jackets • sleeves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improves stiffness of member³¹ • ease of application³¹ • enhanced ductility^{32,33} • high temperature resistance³³ • improved durability³³ • good compatibility with concrete substrate³³ • does not change the predominant failure mode³² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interface slip reduces composite action²² • Increase geometry and member size²⁰ • requires formwork²⁰ • requires surface preparation²⁰ • additional dead load³³ • increased section reduces headroom for bridges crossing roadways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural³³ • shear³³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams³³ • decks • piers³¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural failure with steel yielding and concrete crushing³²
9.	Additional Supports*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduces the span length and maximum positive moment²⁷ • attractive method for upgrading bridge traffic load capacity by widening^{34,35} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • disturbance of the conditions directly below bridge²⁷ • all members require assessment of their capacity to support new load path²⁷ • cost effective with medium to long span bridges thus prohibitive for most short length bridges²⁷ • time consuming construction work³⁴ • use of complicated foundation and use of heavy equipment • expensive³⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural³³ • shear³³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -
10.	Providing continuity*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduces positive moments at mid-spans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces negative moments at connections • requires removal of existing concrete to place negative reinforcement therefore costly construction • traffic disruption due to construction • post-tensioning connection also costly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural • shear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • post-tensioning tendons • self-stressed concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -

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3. Description of the monitoring techniques and their contribution to resilience.

The uncertainties in defining transport asset condition response, properties and loads, during their life-cycle can be reduced by monitoring the structural integrity with measurements that directly estimate the loss of the capacity and functionality [73], [74], [75], [76], [77] [78] estimating indirectly the resistance and robustness of the network. Hence, the challenge in assessing and managing transport infrastructure is associated with the vulnerabilities of the assets, combined with the changeability of climatic and other hazards.

Furthermore, it is widely recognized that Quantitative Risk Analysis (QRA) is important, for the resilience assessment and adaptability of critical transport assets [73], [79]. QRA assists in estimating the potential economic, functional and social losses, determined probabilistically, as a function of hazard, exposure and vulnerability [79], including the associated uncertainties. More recently, quantitative resilience assessment frameworks have been proposed for transport infrastructure exposed to multiple hazards and extreme events [80], [81] which are inclusive of the asset vulnerability and the rapidity of post-event recovery, as described in [Section 2](#) below.

This report provides the link between the components of multiple hazard resilience assessment in transport infrastructure based on a variety of Structural Health and Functionality Monitoring (SHFM) data, and their fusion with models for delivering actionable performance indicators and diagnosis. Breaking that down into the components of risk and resilience this study discusses extensively setting a roadmap on how SHFM data, can provide rapid and reliable measurands of exposure, hazard, vulnerability for the response, recovery and adaptation [82]. This holistic approach in asset management fits squarely into the current vision for delivering resilient-based design and assessment of transport infrastructure [83], [84], [85], [86], [87], [88], [89].

APPENDIX A describes how SHFM can enhance resilience in component, asset and system-level, both for cumulative and abrupt events, in a holistic manner. Also, this part of the report describes how monitoring can enhance the agility and how this improves in a quantifiable manner the resilience. D5 report contains an extensive review of available heterogeneous analogue or digital SHFM systems in transport infrastructure, which are classified based on (i) the nature of the measurand, (ii) their type, (iii) their function principle, (iv) their contribution in risk and resilience assessment and (v) cost.

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Appendix A

A1. Roadmap to monitoring-enhanced resilience management of transport infrastructure

The ability of transport networks to adapt to increased loads and natural and human-induced hazard is dependent on their capacity, redundancy and on the ecosystem, in which they reside. Inherently, it also depends on the condition and life-cycle of assets, the owners' resources for maintenance, monitoring, restoration and adaptation [90]. Throughout the life-cycle of the transport network, resilience may vary due to the complexities and interdependencies [91], [92], [93] within the network and the impacts of multiple hazards [94], [95], [96].

Infrastructure resilience has received a lot of attention in recent years [97], [98], [99], [100]. What has been agreed in these studies is that the uncertainties of all engineering processes, involved in the estimation of resilience is complicated and is causing strong implications for the management of networks and their adaptation to an ever-changing environment [101]. Thus, procedure and activities, such as monitoring using digital technologies, that reduce the uncertainty in resilience evaluation are of paramount importance for the future.

A1.1 Use of monitoring data for enhancing resilience

The resilience of the network is a function of the resilience of its hard assets, e.g. bridges, tunnels, embankments, road pavement, rail tracks, junctions and hubs. Additionally, resilience is dependent on the response of the structural components of which assets comprise, e.g. foundations, slabs, beams, columns, deck, plates, piers, tunnel linings. In this research, no soft assets, such as policies, regulations, procedures have been studied, as this is beyond the scope of this paper, yet recognized that there are strong interdependencies between hard and soft assets influencing the resilience of the transport infrastructure network as a whole.

A1.1.1 Resilience quantification

Figure 1 illustrates the resilience over time for components (Fig. 1A a & b), e.g. beams, columns, slabs, assets (Fig. 1A b & e), e.g. bridges, tunnels, retaining walls, and networks (Fig. 1c & f), e.g. highways and railways for cumulative and abrupt hazard events. The resilience is measured based on different performance indicators that are the capacity for structural component and capacity or functionality for the assets and networks. The fluctuation of resilience is illustrated over time, from the completion of the construction (t_0), up to the end of its designed lifetime (t_{end}^l) or up to the extension of its life-cycle (t_{end}^{ext}). Figures 1a, b & c show the curves for cumulative damage, while Figures 1d, e & f illustrate the case of extreme hazards, which are abrupt and the loss of capacity/functionality is sudden.

Cumulative damage could be the result of ageing, exposure of the infrastructure to adverse environmental conditions or fatigue. Abrupt loss of capacity or functionality can be the aftermath of catastrophic natural and human-induced hazards, such as a (wild)fire. It is noted that the loss of functionality of a transport network under normal circumstances (Fig. 1Ac), e.g. accumulation of damage due to environmental stressors, cannot be substantial, e.g. below the critical functionality level $f_{critical}$, as failures are unlikely to occur simultaneously within the same network. However, this is not the case for networks under extreme circumstances, e.g. extensive flash floods, where a number of assets might fail, the functionality of the network is abruptly and unexpectedly reduced below the critical one.

The black solid lines in Figure 1 illustrate the conventional approach, where only traditional inspections are performed periodically. The red plots illustrate the enhanced resilience models as a result of the deployment of monitoring systems (M). Each segment of the resilience curves is accompanied by the corresponding uncertainty, with an indicative probability density function (PDF). The capacity and

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functionality of components at the beginning of the life-cycle of assets and networks is equal to 1 which is the theoretical design performance. There are different distinct periods at the life-cycle i.e. **1: normal function**, **2: accumulation of damage**, **3: mitigation measures**, **4: bounce back to normal function/adaptation** and potentially life extension. Based on the literature [102], [103], [104], monitoring has the potential to influence the aforementioned periods by a) compressing the post-damage response time, i.e. $t_{resp}^M < t_{resp}^{NM}$, and by reducing the lag time in the strategic planning for decision-making ($t_{resp} - t_{strat}^{pla}$) or the idle time that is the period of no or limited use of the asset or network, b) helping to recover faster, $t_{rec}^M < t_{rec}$ due to prognosis, i.e. better and expedient understanding of the infrastructure condition, c) increasing the reliability of the data, d) permitting recovery to initiate from a level higher than the residual capacity ($c_{resp}^M > c_{residual}$) and fully regain the performance level, and d) enabling timely decision-making and recovery, prior to infrastructure reaching its critical functionality or capacity $c_{critical}$, i.e. $c_{resp}^M > c_{residual}$. Hence, monitoring enables continuous and expedient adaptation to new demands, e.g. climate change ($t_{adapt}^{Mi} < t_{rec}^{p-M} < t_{adapt}^{NMi}$).

The resilience is commonly quantified with a resilience index R, see Equations 1 and 2, which is a function of the time-variant functionality of the infrastructure over time, for the given hazard or stressor [95], [99]. The resilience index of an asset is given by the following equations when the investigated time horizon is the time of adaptation t_{adapt} and t_{adapt}^M after applying mitigation measures for the cases where no (Eq. 1) or enhanced monitoring is used (Eq. 2):

$$R = \frac{1}{t_{adapt}-t_0} \int_{t_0}^{t_{adapt}} Q(t)dt \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$R^M = \frac{1}{t_{adapt}^M-t_0} \int_{t_0}^{t_{adapt}^M} Q(t)dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where $Q(t)$ is the functionality of the asset over time, (see Figure 1g: Nomenclature). Based on the above, resilience with monitoring is greater than without ($R^M > R$). It is noted that the time horizon might be different, e.g. t_{end}^I or t_{end}^{ext} depending on the time window for which resilience is quantified.

A.1.1.2 Monitoring-enhanced resilience

Monitoring systems can also provide timely early warnings [105], [106] after the initiation of the infrastructure deterioration, i.e. t_{resp}^M due to the accumulation of damage or after the loss of capacity following an extreme event at t_{dam}^I . This option provides the opportunity to achieve further adaptation (see the green dashed line after the red-dashed line, $t_{adapt}^{p-M} < t_{adapt}$). The early warnings for a number of assets underperforming or of exceeded capacity or functionality would be the criteria for owners/stakeholders to decide if it is an unacceptable loss of the network (see periods M3, NM3 in Figure 1c & f). They have to decide if measures are to be taken, or if the network will have to continue supporting other important services e.g. energy networks or airport expansions that need to underpin economic activity. Early warnings can also be translated into written warnings to end-users, and/or with variable/dynamic signs along the network area affected.

Figure 1 a to f describes the evolution of the capacity or the capacity/ functionality of the asset or network throughout their lives. The threshold shown in Figure 1a (star) illustrates the case where thresholds have been exceeded and measures have to be taken. At the threshold point at t_{resp}^M the red line is above the black one, which means that the monitored systems are expected to give feedback for better understanding of the capacity/functionality and hence, the estimated resilience is greater when monitoring is embraced if compared to the no monitoring case. If monitoring is performed and early warnings are given, immediate measures can be taken after the time t_{resp}^M . Opposed to the case where the conditions of the component, the asset or the network are unknown, early warning prevents from the continuous degradation below the critical level ($c_{critical}$).

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Even if urgent monitoring measures are taken, it can improve the resilience (shown with the red dashed line) by bouncing back up to its initial performance level. When monitoring is deployed after t_{resp} this will apparently improve the resilience (red dashed line) and at a later time, ideally, will achieve the level of functionality of the case where monitoring is used (red line). For example, a common practice of post-hazard installation of monitoring for cumulative damage is the cathodic protection of reinforcement steel bars with sacrificial anodes [107] to monitor the corrosion rate of the steel bars. The impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP) systems follow the propagation of corrosion of the steel bars by monitoring the current flow and voltage, helping to define more accurately the reinforcement ratio lost due to corrosion. This evidence can aid in both mitigating the corrosion (stressor) and also facilitate model updating or more reliable estimations of the capacity of the structural member and enable decisions for appropriate measures during recovery.

The ultimate goal of the resilience-based management of the network is mainly the ability of the transport network to adapt to increased demands, e.g. due to climate change, (see green line in Figures 1 a to f) and hence the resilience of an asset is secondary as long as the resilience level of the network is being met. In other words, if the initial demand for example of 10,000 vehicles per day is being met, this means that the resilience of the network is equal to one. However, if this demand increases, indirectly the resilience of the entire network will be reduced. Hence, pushing the threshold of the demands upwards leads in increased requirements for adaptation to achieve the same level of resilience. To meet this requirement, the asset and/or network require restoration, in the form of updates, improvements, upgrades and continuous adaptation that can take place along the periods NM2 onwards. Analogously to cumulative damage, Figures 1 d-f show the resilience model for extreme events based on the same rationale.

A.2 Holistic dimension of infrastructure management for enhanced resilience

Figure 2A encapsulates the roadmap to resilience-based design and assessment of transport infrastructure. The four components of this holistic [108], resilience-based management take into consideration both local and global scale of individual parts (components and assets) as well as the network as a whole. The first component is the **engineering, e.g. the structural part (grey circle)**, which contains the design, construction, application, loads, events, properties, geometry and exposure. The second component is the **monitoring part (blue circle)**, e.g. the structural health, functionality, and monitoring of the ecosystem, including visualisation, inspection, quantification, characterisation and damage detection. The **risk and management component follow (red circle)**, quantifying and describing the risk analysis, the quantification of the associated losses, to facilitate future predictions enabling model-updating for well-documented and objective decision-making and planning. In this step, the **communication of risk** to end-users is also included, mainly a responsibility of infrastructure owners and operators. The last step of this holistic approach is shown with the outer circle, which illustrates the **delivery** of resilience with optimised services and adaptation toward economic growth, accounting for any limitations in resources (**green circle**). The arrows between the homocentric circles indicate a dynamic and continuous dataflow between the components of the approach and its complexities.

In the flowchart of Figure 3A, the roadmap for delivering resilience in life-cycle of critical infrastructure aided by monitoring systems is fully described with all the sub-procedures noted with different colours. The roadmap includes the **hazards**, which may be any natural or human-induced stressor, the **exposure** that is the infrastructure assets, networks or a non-engineering exposure such as businesses, services and mobility, the **interactions** with the affected end-users and environment, and the **adaptation** to these interactions and hazards. Subsequently, the roadmap describes all cyclic sub-procedures and activities. In this logic procedure, the infrastructure is designed, delivered, monitored and assessed, taking into consideration stressors (upper grey box), in an effort to perform monitoring-based infrastructure management (middle blue box). By lowering risks and delivering uninterrupted mobility, investments

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and/or resource allocation are optimised. By maximising the resilience of the network, economic activities are underpinned but the citizens and the environment are safeguarded (lower green box). The sub-procedures/activities that are illustrated in the flowchart follow the colours and therefore the categories of the holistic approach described above (Figure 2A). The categories include grey colours for structural activities, blue boxes for monitoring activities, orange and red for risk assessment & management and resilience activities and green colours for delivering sustainable and resilience infrastructure.

Transport infrastructure is expected to operate in normal circumstances but is also expected to withstand stressors when **exposed** to various, multiple natural and/or human-induced hazards and extreme events. Throughout its lifecycle, after the completion of construction, infrastructure interacts with the environment, comprising together with the natural environment and ecosystem, whilst also influences the adjacent built environment, e.g. energy, utility, urban and other transport networks [109], [110]. Figure 3 shows the normal **design** phase, during which the external stressors due to interactions, are taken into consideration. During all the structural activities, the type of asset, its geometry, the materials and the properties are selected considering the expected performance and the exposure, typically by meeting the design criteria set up in design guidelines [111], [112]. After the construction phase, a **monitoring strategy** might be decided and deployed on the basis of the types of measurands, methods and systems, time, periodicity or continuity of measurements. For the first time, the core and essential procedure of monitoring is emphasized, which design guidelines and proper asset management neglect to point out. With monitoring, as part of digital innovation in transport infrastructure, the data collection and interpretation is performed, defining the structural integrity and the level of operability and/or functionality of the networks. The **interpretation** of the data is a first assessment of the extent or severity of the identified damage and the potential risk of the condition.

Decision-making, represented by diamonds in the flow chart, is performed having **safety** as the main criterion. This is either followed by updating the monitoring strategy in the case of acceptable risk or either by further risk assessment when the condition is non-acceptable. Recently, the operations of the transport networks have increasing demands and the requirements, except for safety, have been shifted toward minimal tolerance to traffic disruptions. This shift is also expressed by the requirement for enhanced **resilience**, both locally (component) and globally (asset). In case that the integrity, operability or functionality is in question, further evaluation of the risk is performed. This evaluation inherently includes the input uncertainties as these are integrated into the fragility and degradation models, as described in the orange activities (updated design& assessment model) of the flow chart. The estimated level of **risk** defines the asset operability, and in this case, monitoring can continue, thus the risk is acceptable. For the assets that have the greatest impact to the resilience of the network, projections of the risk to the future may lead to the need for additional adaptation measures e.g. for climate deviations, increase in requirements, deterioration. Otherwise, the next step is to take **mitigation measures**, when the risk is unacceptable. The nature of the measures varies and spans from decisions for **communicating risk** to stakeholders, up to legislation changes, as a means to protect the infrastructure, the environment or ownership and property, measures aiming at addressing inadequacies due to amendments in design guideline requirements. Measures might include engineering restoration, covering tasks and additional secondary direct or indirect works, for example, use of additional signalling to reduce risk due to slippery road surface. These mitigation measures may lead to additional measures toward adaptation, which will render the asset back to its original performance. This adaptation might also embrace updating of the monitoring strategy by adding e.g. new and/or upgraded sensors.

The roadmap also prescribes improvements of both the **monitoring** strategy and the infrastructure **models** throughout the lifespan of the transport system, if resources are available. These upgrades may be aided by **emerging technologies**, e.g. Building Information Modelling (BIM) [113], [114], [115], Internet of Things (IoT) [116], [117] or Digital Twins (DT), Machine Learning (ML) [118] and Artificial Intelligence (AI) [119], [120], [121] among others. These technologies are valuable tools

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providing intelligence during the risk assessment, interpretation and decision-making (orange sub-procedure). They enable processing big data and permit the development of models for predicting future combined events. The augmented reliability level helps trigger early warnings. Digital monitoring can further facilitate early warnings [122] permitting optimum, safe and non-disrupted traffic, as a means to minimising economic and human losses.

A.3 Use of emerging monitoring technologies in risk management and adaptation

It is expected that future developments will include the integration of new technologies in the data-driven risk and resilience assessment of transport infrastructure towards adaptation to changing environment and future demands (see Emerging Technology in Figure 3A).

Machine Learning (ML) techniques can reduce drastically the time and resources required for efficient model updating and generation of vulnerability and resilience models. ML has been utilised successfully to date for the rapid seismic fragility assessment of bridges [123], [124]. However, ML can also be employed for the resilience assessment of infrastructure exposed to diverse hazards and can be enhanced by monitoring data. Liang et al. [126] investigated the use of ML algorithms for evaluating the serviceability of bridges using combined SHFM data generated by external loads, such as wind and traffic flows, hyperspectral images and moisture measurements of the structural components. [125] explain how Big Data and cloud computing can be utilised in real-time decision-making for critical bridges based on SHM data, including communication of warning messages to drivers via Variable Message Signs (VMS) to cell phones. BIM is also expected to be utilised extensively in risk and resilience management, not only during the design and construction of transport infrastructure projects, but also during their maintenance, design of mitigation measures and extension of lifetime [127]. Yet, a knowledge gap existing in the integration of BIM technologies with traditional risk management.

In the near future, ML and BIM are expected to cooperate and complement IoT technologies [128] for delivering smart transport infrastructure, toward providing efficient transport functions and new services to the end-users. Inevitably, IoT and related technologies, e.g. AI, data analytics, may assist transport infrastructure owners and operators in monitoring and managing ageing structures more effectively in almost real-time. For example, Whyte et al. [129] explored the feasibility of using digital twins for providing insights into infrastructure system interdependencies. The research embraced practical identification, prioritisation and management of system interoperability.

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(g) Nomenclature:

1	————	no monitoring- recovery to levels lower than the designed one
2	————	continuous monitoring from the beginning of infrastructure operation
3	- - - - -	monitoring during the recovery period
4	————	no monitoring- recovery back to the original capacity
5	- - - - -	adaptation with monitoring
6	- - - - -	adaptation with monitoring after full recovery
7	- - - - -	extension of life
t_0		time of asset or network at its completion and initiation of operation
t_{dam}^I		time at the initiation of significant accumulation of damage
t_{strat}^{pla}		time at the initiation of strategic planning for mitigation
t_{resp}		time at response, i.e. initiation of mitigation measures - no monitoring
t_{rec}		time at recovery of capacity or functionality after the application of mitigation measures - no monitoring
t_{end}^I		end of life-cycle according to the initial design
C_{rec}		capacity or functionality after mitigation measures are taken - no monitoring at t_{rec}
C_{resp}^M		critical capacity or functionality according to the design leading to mitigation measures - with monitoring
$C/f_{critical}$		critical capacity or functionality according to the design and application of mitigation measures - no monitoring
$C_{residual}$		post-event residual capacity or functionality - no monitoring
$C_{residual}^M$		post-event residual capacity or functionality - with monitoring
t_{resp}^M		response time at decision for taking mitigation measures - with monitoring
t_{rec}^M		time at recovery of capacity or functionality after the application of the mitigation measures - with monitoring
t_{rec}^{D-M}		time at recovery of capacity or functionality after the application of the mitigation measures - with post-disaster monitoring at the restoration period
$t_{rec}^{100\%}$		time at recovery of the initial capacity or functionality level after the application of the mitigation measures - with post-disaster monitoring at the restoration period
t_{adapt}^{D-M}		time at adaptation of capacity or functionality - with post-disastrous monitoring
t_{adapt}^{NMi}		time at every adaptation of capacity or functionality - with no monitoring

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Figure 1A. Resilience curve of (a) components, (b) assets and (c) transport networks throughout their life-cycle due to cumulative damages, e.g. ageing, corrosion, fatigue, scour, ground movements and settlements, deflections, increased traffic (see *1a,b,c*), natural and human-induced hazards, e.g. seismic events, flash floods, landslide and fire (see *1d,e,f*) and figure nomenclature (*1g*).

Figure 2A. Holistic approach for delivering monitoring-based resilient infrastructure.

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Figure 3A. Roadmap for delivering monitoring-based resilience in life-cycle assessment of infrastructure